

R code and output for ‘How to use statistics to claim antagonism and synergism from binary mixture experiments’

Revised version, IA results for Data example 1 slightly changed

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June 3 2021

Preliminaries

Session information:

```
sessionInfo()
```

```
## R version 4.0.3 (2020-10-10)
## Platform: x86_64-pc-linux-gnu (64-bit)
## Running under: Ubuntu 20.04.2 LTS
##
## Matrix products: default
## BLAS: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/blas/libblas.so.3.9.0
## LAPACK: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/lapack/liblapack.so.3.9.0
##
## locale:
## [1] LC_CTYPE=da_DK.UTF-8      LC_NUMERIC=C
## [3] LC_TIME=da_DK.UTF-8      LC_COLLATE=da_DK.UTF-8
## [5] LC_MONETARY=da_DK.UTF-8  LC_MESSAGES=da_DK.UTF-8
## [7] LC_PAPER=da_DK.UTF-8    LC_NAME=C
## [9] LC_ADDRESS=C            LC_TELEPHONE=C
## [11] LC_MEASUREMENT=da_DK.UTF-8 LC_IDENTIFICATION=C
##
## attached base packages:
## [1] stats      graphics  grDevices  utils      datasets  methods   base
##
## other attached packages:
## [1] rmarkdown_2.6
##
## loaded via a namespace (and not attached):
## [1] digest_0.6.27  crayon_1.4.1    IRdisplay_1.0  repr_1.1.3
## [5] lifecycle_1.0.0 jsonlite_1.7.2  magrittr_2.0.1 evaluate_0.14
## [9] pillar_1.4.7   stringi_1.5.3   rlang_0.4.10   uuid_0.1-4
## [13] ellipsis_0.3.1 IRkernel_1.1.1  tools_4.0.3    stringr_1.4.0
## [17] yaml_2.2.1     xfun_0.21       compiler_4.0.3 base64enc_0.1-3
## [21] htmltools_0.5.1.1 pbdZMQ_0.3-5    knitr_1.31
```

Package activation (these **R** are needed below):

```
library(devtools)
install_github("DoseResponse/drcData")
library(drcData)
```

```
library(car)
library(drc)
library(multcomp)
library(plyr)
```

Note that the data used in the 2 examples are found in the package *drcData*.

Data example 1

Data in this example are binomial and obtained from a binary mixture experiment that involves multiple single-dose factorial designs where the insecticide imidacloprid is combined with each of 7 pesticides in turn. Each of the 7 single-dose experiments is analyzed separately (for simplicity; a simultaneous model could also be fitted but results would remain the same).

Data formatting

The treatment variable needs to be encoded as a categorical variable using the function `as.factor()` and, moreover, the control group (“H2O”) is defined as the reference using the function `relevel()`. A column containing the number of bees per cage is added.

```
bees[["treat"]] <- as.factor(bees[["treat"]])
bees[["treat"]] <- relevel(bees[["treat"]], "H2O")

bees[["gtotal"]] <- rep(25, nrow(bees))

head(bees, 12)
```

```
##      mixture      treat rep dead0h dead48h gtotal
## 1      CK-1      H2O    1      0      0      25
## 2      CK-2      H2O    2      2      2      25
## 3      CK-3      H2O    3      5      5      25
## 4  AdvBra  Advi274B    1      2      5      25
## 5  AdvBra  Advi274B    2      0      6      25
## 6  AdvBra  Advi274B    3      0      3      25
## 7  AdvBra  Brack91    1      3     10      25
## 8  AdvBra  Brack91    2      0     11      25
## 9  AdvBra  Brack91    3      1      7      25
## 10 AdvBra  AdviBrack    1      0     20      25
## 11 AdvBra  AdviBrack    2      0     16      25
## 12 AdvBra  AdviBrack    3      0      9      25
```

Model fitting

Below we fit two-way ANOVA-models to binomial dose-response data using the **R** function `glm()`. Appropriate subsets are extracted to ensure that data from single-dose experiments are indeed fitted. The `coef` and `summary` methods are used for extracting parameter estimates, standard error and other output from the model fits (in case of `summary`).

Model fit for imidacloprid combined with acephate (Bracket97):

```
bees.advbra <- glm(cbind(dead48h, gtotal - dead48h) ~ treat - 1,
                  data = bees[1:12, ], family = binomial)
summary(bees.advbra)
```

```
##
## Call:
```

```
## glm(formula = cbind(dead48h, gtotal - dead48h) ~ treat - 1, family = binomial,
##   data = bees[1:12, ])
##
## Deviance Residuals:
##   Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.4177  -0.9235   0.2220   0.6672   2.1391
##
## Coefficients:
##             Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## treatH20        -2.2736     0.3969  -5.728 1.02e-08 ***
## treatAdvi274B   -1.4718     0.2963  -4.967 6.82e-07 ***
## treatAdviBrack    0.4055     0.2357   1.720  0.0854 .
## treatBrack91    -0.5179     0.2387  -2.170  0.0300 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## (Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)
##
##   Null deviance: 118.053  on 12  degrees of freedom
## Residual deviance:  20.952  on  8  degrees of freedom
## AIC: 65.542
##
## Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5
```

```
coef(summary(bees.advbra))
```

```
##             Estimate Std. Error  z value    Pr(>|z|)
## treatH20        -2.2735976  0.3969421 -5.727782 1.017524e-08
## treatAdvi274B   -1.4718165  0.2963478 -4.966518 6.816586e-07
## treatAdviBrack    0.4054651  0.2357023  1.720243 8.538832e-02
## treatBrack91    -0.5179431  0.2387276 -2.169598 3.003728e-02
```

Note also that overdispersion seems to be present (most likely due to the cage variation) and, if adjusted for (using *quasibinomial* rather than *binomial* in `glm()`), it will inflate standard errors.

Model fit for imidacloprid combined with λ -Cyhalothrin (Karate Z 2.08 CS)

```
bees.advkar <- glm(cbind(dead48h, gtotal - dead48h) ~ treat - 1,
                  data = bees[c(1:3, 13:21), ], family = binomial)
summary(bees.advkar)
```

```
##
## Call:
## glm(formula = cbind(dead48h, gtotal - dead48h) ~ treat - 1, family = binomial,
##   data = bees[c(1:3, 13:21), ])
##
## Deviance Residuals:
##   Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.21337  -1.03440   0.08479   0.72233   1.61706
##
## Coefficients:
##             Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## treatH20        -2.2736     0.3969  -5.728 1.02e-08 ***
## treatAdvi274K   -1.4718     0.2963  -4.967 6.82e-07 ***
## treatAdviKara   -1.2272     0.2758  -4.450 8.60e-06 ***
## treatKarat273   -3.1781     0.5893  -5.393 6.92e-08 ***
```

```

## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## (Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)
##
## Null deviance: 208.74 on 12 degrees of freedom
## Residual deviance: 17.06 on 8 degrees of freedom
## AIC: 54.418
##
## Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5
coef(summary(bees.advkar))

##           Estimate Std. Error  z value    Pr(>|z|)
## treatH2O      -2.273598  0.3969421 -5.727782 1.017524e-08
## treatAdvi274K -1.471817  0.2963478 -4.966518 6.816586e-07
## treatAdviKara -1.227230  0.2757987 -4.449730 8.597826e-06
## treatKarat273 -3.178054  0.5892556 -5.393336 6.916136e-08

Model fit for imidacloprid combined with oxamyl (Vydate 3.77 CLV)
bees.advvyd <- glm(cbind(dead48h, gtotal - dead48h) ~ treat - 1,
                  data = bees[c(1:3, 22:30), ], family = binomial)
summary(bees.advvyd)

##
## Call:
## glm(formula = cbind(dead48h, gtotal - dead48h) ~ treat - 1, family = binomial,
##      data = bees[c(1:3, 22:30), ])
##
## Deviance Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.2134  -0.9799  -0.2697   0.8580   2.1391
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## treatH2O      -2.2736    0.3969  -5.728 1.02e-08 ***
## treatAdvi274V -1.4718    0.2963  -4.967 6.82e-07 ***
## treatAdviVyda  0.4055    0.2357   1.720 0.085388 .
## treatVydat162 -1.0116    0.2611  -3.874 0.000107 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## (Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)
##
## Null deviance: 128.566 on 12 degrees of freedom
## Residual deviance: 19.348 on 8 degrees of freedom
## AIC: 63.412
##
## Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5
coef(summary(bees.advvyd))

##           Estimate Std. Error  z value    Pr(>|z|)
## treatH2O      -2.2735976  0.3969421 -5.727782 1.017524e-08
## treatAdvi274V -1.4718165  0.2963478 -4.966518 6.816586e-07
## treatAdviVyda  0.4054651  0.2357023  1.720243 8.538832e-02

```

```

## treatVydat162 -1.0116009 0.2611165 -3.874137 1.070034e-04
Model fit for imidacloprid combined with tetraconazole (Domark 230 ME)
bees.advdom <- glm(cbind(dead48h, gtotal - dead48h) ~ treat - 1,
                  data = bees[c(1:3, 31:39), ], family = binomial)
summary(bees.advdom)

##
## Call:
## glm(formula = cbind(dead48h, gtotal - dead48h) ~ treat - 1, family = binomial,
##      data = bees[c(1:3, 31:39), ])
##
## Deviance Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.2134  -0.9509  -0.3421   0.6995   2.1444
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## treatH2O          -2.2736     0.3969  -5.728 1.02e-08 ***
## treatAdvi274D    -1.4718     0.2963  -4.967 6.82e-07 ***
## treatAdviDoma    -0.2955     0.2335  -1.266  0.206
## treatDoma2500    -2.1253     0.3741  -5.681 1.34e-08 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## (Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)
##
##      Null deviance: 160.791  on 12  degrees of freedom
## Residual deviance:  16.909  on  8  degrees of freedom
## AIC: 59.085
##
## Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5
coef(summary(bees.advdom))

##              Estimate Std. Error  z value    Pr(>|z|)
## treatH2O          -2.2735976   0.3969421  -5.727782 1.017524e-08
## treatAdvi274D    -1.4718165   0.2963478  -4.966518 6.816586e-07
## treatAdviDoma    -0.2954642   0.2334648  -1.265562 2.056699e-01
## treatDoma2500    -2.1252511   0.3740660  -5.681487 1.335288e-08
Model fit for imidacloprid combined with sulfoxaflor (Transform 5G)
bees.advtra <- glm(cbind(dead48h, gtotal - dead48h) ~ treat - 1,
                  data = bees[c(1:3, 40:48), ], family = binomial)
summary(bees.advtra)

##
## Call:
## glm(formula = cbind(dead48h, gtotal - dead48h) ~ treat - 1, family = binomial,
##      data = bees[c(1:3, 40:48), ])
##
## Deviance Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.21337  -0.83346  -0.03241   0.76826   1.61706
##

```

```

## Coefficients:
##           Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## treatH2O      -2.2736    0.3969  -5.728 1.02e-08 ***
## treatAdvi274T -1.4718    0.2963  -4.967 6.82e-07 ***
## treatAdviTran -0.5179    0.2387  -2.170    0.03 *
## treatTrans117 -2.4423    0.4256  -5.738 9.57e-09 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## (Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)
##
## Null deviance: 171.410 on 12 degrees of freedom
## Residual deviance: 15.173 on 8 degrees of freedom
## AIC: 56.208
##
## Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5
coef(summary(bees.advtra))

##           Estimate Std. Error  z value    Pr(>|z|)
## treatH2O      -2.2735976  0.3969421 -5.727782 1.017524e-08
## treatAdvi274T -1.4718165  0.2963478 -4.966518 6.816586e-07
## treatAdviTran -0.5179431  0.2387276 -2.169598 3.003728e-02
## treatTrans117 -2.4423470  0.4256283 -5.738216 9.567889e-09

Model fit for imidacloprid combined with glyphosate (Roundup)
bees.advrou <- glm(cbind(dead48h, gtotal - dead48h) ~ relevel(treat, "H2O") - 1,
                  data = bees[c(1:3, 58:66)], family = binomial)
summary(bees.advrou)

##
## Call:
## glm(formula = cbind(dead48h, gtotal - dead48h) ~ relevel(treat,
## "H2O") - 1, family = binomial, data = bees[c(1:3, 58:66),
## ])
##
## Deviance Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.21337  -0.40154  -0.00012   0.29273   1.61706
##
## Coefficients:
##           Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## relevel(treat, "H2O")H2O      -2.2736    0.3969  -5.728 1.02e-08 ***
## relevel(treat, "H2O")Advi274R -1.4718    0.2963  -4.967 6.82e-07 ***
## relevel(treat, "H2O")AdviRoun -1.4718    0.2963  -4.967 6.82e-07 ***
## relevel(treat, "H2O")Roun2500 -21.9626  4115.6448  -0.005    0.996
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## (Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)
##
## Null deviance: 241.249 on 12 degrees of freedom
## Residual deviance: 16.294 on 8 degrees of freedom
## AIC: 48.367
##

```

```
## Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 18
```

```
coef(summary(bees.advrou))
```

```
##              Estimate Std. Error   z value   Pr(>|z|)
## relevel(treat, "H20")H20      -2.273598    0.3969421 -5.727781447 1.017525e-08
## relevel(treat, "H20")Advi274R -1.471817    0.2963478 -4.966517627 6.816586e-07
## relevel(treat, "H20")AdviRoun -1.471817    0.2963478 -4.966517627 6.816586e-07
## relevel(treat, "H20")Roun2500 -21.962590  4115.6448170 -0.005336367 9.957422e-01
```

Note the large negative estimate for the control caused by 100% survival in the control group. No reference effect can be estimated reliably (even though **R** produces some output).

Model fit for imidacloprid combined with clothianidin (Belay)

```
bees.advbel <- glm(cbind(dead48h, gtotal - dead48h) ~ relevel(treat, "H20") - 1,
                  data = bees[c(1:3, 49:57)], family = binomial)
summary(bees.advbel)
```

```
##
## Call:
## glm(formula = cbind(dead48h, gtotal - dead48h) ~ relevel(treat,
##   "H20") - 1, family = binomial, data = bees[c(1:3, 49:57),
##   ])
##
## Deviance Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -2.2134  -0.8857   0.2576   0.4838   1.6171
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## relevel(treat, "H20")H20      -2.2736    0.3969  -5.728 1.02e-08 ***
## relevel(treat, "H20")Adv274BL -1.4718    0.2963  -4.967 6.82e-07 ***
## relevel(treat, "H20")AdviBela -0.7538    0.2475  -3.045 0.00233 **
## relevel(treat, "H20")Belay40  -1.5622    0.3050  -5.121 3.04e-07 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## (Dispersion parameter for binomial family taken to be 1)
##
##      Null deviance: 146.601  on 12  degrees of freedom
## Residual deviance:  12.643  on  8  degrees of freedom
## AIC: 55.725
##
## Number of Fisher Scoring iterations: 5
coef(summary(bees.advbel))
```

```
##              Estimate Std. Error   z value   Pr(>|z|)
## relevel(treat, "H20")H20      -2.2735976    0.3969421 -5.727782 1.017524e-08
## relevel(treat, "H20")Adv274BL -1.4718165    0.2963478 -4.966518 6.816586e-07
## relevel(treat, "H20")AdviBela -0.7537718    0.2475369 -3.045089 2.326116e-03
## relevel(treat, "H20")Belay40  -1.5621850    0.3050444 -5.121172 3.036426e-07
```

Defining helper function

Once two-way ANOVA-type models have been fitted to the binomial data the **R** function defined below is used for calculating differences between observed mixture effects and predicted mixture effects under the assumptions of dose addition and independent action.

The resulting differences (along with the corresponding standard errors and 95% confidence intervals) are on the probability scale (estimates are appropriately back-transformed from the log-odds scale).

```
listFct <- function(modelFit)
{
  returnMat <- matrix(NA, 2, 4)

  paramMF <- coef(modelFit)
  names(paramMF) <- letters[1:4]

  returnMat[1, ] <-
    unlist(
      deltaMethod(paramMF,
                  "exp(c)/(1+exp(c)) - exp(b)/(1+exp(b)) - exp(d)/(1+exp(d)) + exp(a)/(1+exp(a))",
                  vcov(modelFit)))
  # Diff: DA

  returnMat[2, ] <- unlist(deltaMethod(paramMF,
                                      "exp(c)/(1+exp(c)) - ( exp(b)/(1+exp(b)) * exp(d)/(1+exp(d)) ) / (exp(a)/(1+exp(a)))",
                                      vcov(modelFit)))
  # Diff: IA (updated from version 2!)

  colnames(returnMat) <- c("Est", "SE", "CIL", "CIU")
  as.data.frame(cbind(met = c("DA-Diff", "IA-Diff"), round(returnMat, digits = 3)))
}
```

Note that this helper function exploits the specific order of estimates from the model fits obtained below. This order may be different for different datasets and the helper function would need to be modified accordingly.

Extracting relevant estimates

Below, the helper function is applied to all 7 model fits in one go.

```
ex1.results <- ldply(list(ace = bees.advbra,
                        lam = bees.advkar,
                        oxa = bees.advvyd,
                        tet = bees.advdom,
                        sul = bees.advtra,
                        gly = bees.advrou,
                        clo = bees.advbel), listFct)
```

To get more easily readable output we retrieve results for dose addition and independent action separately.

Estimated differences under the assumption of dose addition (selecting every second row starting from row 1:

```
ex1.results[c(1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13), ]
```

```
##   .id   met   Est   SE   CIL   CIU
## 1 ace DA-Diff 0.133 0.097 -0.057 0.324
## 3 lam DA-Diff 0.093 0.077 -0.059 0.245
## 5 oxa DA-Diff 0.24 0.095 0.054 0.426
## 7 tet DA-Diff 0.227 0.088 0.055 0.398
```

```
## 9 sul DA-Diff 0.2 0.085 0.033 0.367
## 11 gly DA-Diff 0.093 0.072 -0.048 0.234
## 13 clo DA-Diff 0.053 0.089 -0.122 0.228
```

Estimated differences under the assumption of independent action (selecting every second row starting from row 2):

```
ex1.results[c(2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14), ]
```

```
## .id met Est SE CIL CIU
## 2 ace IA-Diff -0.147 0.347 -0.826 0.533
## 4 lam IA-Diff 0.147 0.075 0 0.293
## 6 oxa IA-Diff 0.067 0.259 -0.441 0.574
## 8 tet IA-Diff 0.213 0.13 -0.041 0.468
## 10 sul IA-Diff 0.213 0.109 0 0.427
## 12 gly IA-Diff 0.187 0.045 0.098 0.275
## 14 clo IA-Diff -0.027 0.182 -0.383 0.33
```

Data example 2

Data in this example are binomial and obtained from a binary mixture experiment that was based on a fixed-ratio design involving 5 rays: the 2 rays for the pesticides prochloraz and alpha-cypermethrin and 3 mixture rays corresponding to virtual mixture proportions of 25:75, 50:50, and 75:25. For each of the 5 rays, a separate dose-response model was fitted. In this case, fitting a simultaneous model is also possible and results will be close but not exactly the same (due to the different assumption about the residual error terms).

Data

The dataset is found in the package *drcData*:

```
head(Daphnia)
```

```
## dose.a dose.p dose mix.frac total immob48
## 1 1.50 0 1.50 0 5 5
## 2 1.50 0 1.50 0 5 5
## 3 1.50 0 1.50 0 5 4
## 4 1.50 0 1.50 0 5 5
## 5 0.75 0 0.75 0 5 5
## 6 0.75 0 0.75 0 5 5
```

Model fitting

Below, dose-response models are fitted to each ray assuming a two-parameter log-logistic model for binomial dose-response data. The models are fitted using the function `drm()` from the **R** package *drc*. The plot and summary methods are used for showing the resulting parameter estimates and, for one ray, the resulting fitted curve.

```
Daphnia0.00.LL.2 <- drm(immob48/total ~ dose, data = subset(Daphnia, mix.frac == 0),
                      fct = LL.2(), type = "binomial", weights = total)
summary(Daphnia0.00.LL.2)
```

```
##
## Model fitted: Log-logistic (ED50 as parameter) with lower limit at 0 and upper limit at 1 (2 parms)
##
## Parameter estimates:
##
##           Estimate Std. Error t-value p-value
```

```
## b:(Intercept) -2.082143  0.352239 -5.9112 3.397e-09 ***
## e:(Intercept)  0.297053  0.038904  7.6355 2.246e-14 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
plot(Daphnia0.00.LL.2)
```



```
Daphnia0.25.LL.2 <- drm(immob48/total ~ dose, data = subset(Daphnia, mix.frac == 0.25),
  fct = LL.2(), type = "binomial", weights = total)
summary(Daphnia0.25.LL.2)
```

```
##
## Model fitted: Log-logistic (ED50 as parameter) with lower limit at 0 and upper limit at 1 (2 parms)
##
## Parameter estimates:
##
##           Estimate Std. Error t-value  p-value
## b:(Intercept) -3.00529   0.57367 -5.2387 1.617e-07 ***
## e:(Intercept) 280.09493  30.42752  9.2053 < 2.2e-16 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
Daphnia0.50.LL.2 <- drm(immob48/total ~ dose, data = subset(Daphnia, mix.frac == 0.5),
  fct = LL.2(), type = "binomial", weights = total)
summary(Daphnia0.50.LL.2)
```

```
##
## Model fitted: Log-logistic (ED50 as parameter) with lower limit at 0 and upper limit at 1 (2 parms)
##
## Parameter estimates:
##
##           Estimate Std. Error t-value  p-value
## b:(Intercept) -3.22748   0.60331 -5.3496 8.814e-08 ***
## e:(Intercept) 123.95836  12.82223  9.6675 < 2.2e-16 ***
```

```

## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Daphnia0.75.LL.2 <- drm(immob48/total ~ dose, data = subset(Daphnia, mix.frac == 0.75),
                      fct = LL.2(), type = "binomial", weights = total)
summary(Daphnia0.75.LL.2)

##
## Model fitted: Log-logistic (ED50 as parameter) with lower limit at 0 and upper limit at 1 (2 parms)
##
## Parameter estimates:
##
##           Estimate Std. Error t-value  p-value
## b:(Intercept) -7.4794      1.7924 -4.1727 3.01e-05 ***
## e:(Intercept)  98.8071      8.1315 12.1511 < 2.2e-16 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Daphnia1.00.LL.2 <- drm(immob48/total ~ dose, data = subset(Daphnia, mix.frac == 1),
                      fct = LL.2(), type = "binomial", weights = total)
summary(Daphnia1.00.LL.2)

##
## Model fitted: Log-logistic (ED50 as parameter) with lower limit at 0 and upper limit at 1 (2 parms)
##
## Parameter estimates:
##
##           Estimate Std. Error t-value  p-value
## b:(Intercept) -3.61416      0.72248 -5.0024 5.661e-07 ***
## e:(Intercept) 4941.80727    477.42241 10.3510 < 2.2e-16 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

Combining estimated ED50 values

The relevant parameter estimates (for ED50 in this case but could be any ED value) and standard errors are retrieved from the individual model fits and arranged in a results matrix named ED50res (which also contains the mixture fraction in the first column).

```

ED50res <- matrix(NA, 5, 3)
ED50res[, 1] <- c(0, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 1)

ED50res[1, 2:3] <- ED(Daphnia0.00.LL.2, 50, display = FALSE)
ED50res[2, 2:3] <- ED(Daphnia0.25.LL.2, 50, display = FALSE)
ED50res[3, 2:3] <- ED(Daphnia0.50.LL.2, 50, display = FALSE)
ED50res[4, 2:3] <- ED(Daphnia0.75.LL.2, 50, display = FALSE)
ED50res[5, 2:3] <- ED(Daphnia1.00.LL.2, 50, display = FALSE)

colnames(ED50res) <- c("f", "Est", "SE")
ED50res <- as.data.frame(ED50res)
ED50res

```

```

##      f      Est      SE
## 1 0.00  0.2970528 0.03890397
## 2 0.25 280.0949250 30.42752346
## 3 0.50 123.9583605 12.82222850
## 4 0.75  98.8070887  8.13152832

```

```
## 5 1.00 4941.8072670 477.42240984
```

Defining helper functions

Once dose-response models have been fitted 2 **R** helper functions are defined for calculating differences and ratios that compare estimated ED50 values to predicted ED50 values under the assumptions of dose addition and independent action, respectively.

The resulting differences and ratios (along with the corresponding standard errors and 95% confidence intervals) are on the probability scale (estimates are appropriately back-transformed from the log-odds scale):

```
diffApplyFct <- function(rowElt, comp1, comp2)
{
  estVal <- rowElt[2] - rowElt[1] * ED50res[comp1, 2] - (1 - rowElt[1]) * ED50res[comp2, 2]
  seVal <- sqrt(rowElt[3]^2 + (rowElt[1]^2) * (ED50res[comp1, 3]^2) +
                ((1 - rowElt[1])^2) * (ED50res[comp2, 3]^2))
  retVec <- c(estVal, seVal, estVal - 1.96*seVal, estVal + 1.96*seVal)
  names(retVec) <- c("diff", "se", "ci.l", "ci.u")
  retVec
}

ratApplyFct <- function(rowElt, comp1, comp2)
{
  estVal <- rowElt[2] / (rowElt[1] * ED50res[comp1, 2] + (1 - rowElt[1]) * ED50res[comp2, 2])
  deNom <- (rowElt[1] * ED50res[comp1, 2] + (1 - rowElt[1]) * ED50res[comp2, 2])^2
  seVal <- sqrt((rowElt[3]^2) / deNom + (rowElt[2]^2 * (rowElt[1]^2) * ED50res[comp1, 3] +
                rowElt[2]^2 * ((1-rowElt[1])^2) * ED50res[comp2, 3]) / (deNom^2))
  retVec <- c(estVal, seVal, estVal - 1.96*seVal, estVal + 1.96*seVal)
  names(retVec) <- c("ratio", "se", "ci.l", "ci.u")
  retVec
}
```

Extracting relevant estimates

Estimated differences for the 3 mixture rays are extracted (-c(1, 5) means omitting the rows with meaningless results for the individual pesticides) are extracted using the helper function diffApplyFct():

```
estDiff <- cbind(f = ED50res[, 1],
                 t(apply(ED50res, 1, diffApplyFct, comp1 = 5, comp2 = 1)))[-c(1, 5), ]
estDiff
```

```
##          f          diff          se          ci.l          ci.u
## [1,] 0.25 -955.5797 123.1730 -1196.999 -714.1605
## [2,] 0.50 -2347.0938 239.0553 -2815.642 -1878.5454
## [3,] 0.75 -3607.6226 358.1591 -4309.615 -2905.6307
```

Likewise, the estimated ratios are shown extracted (using the helper function ratApplyFct()) as follows:

```
estRatios <- cbind(f = ED50res[, 1],
                  t(apply(ED50res, 1, ratApplyFct, comp1 = 5, comp2 = 1)))[-c(1, 5), ]
estRatios
```

```
##          f          ratio          se          ci.l          ci.u
## [1,] 0.25 0.22667369 0.024644615 0.17837025 0.27497714
## [2,] 0.50 0.05016420 0.005193713 0.03998452 0.06034388
## [3,] 0.75 0.02665829 0.002197062 0.02235205 0.03096453
```